

5 ABSTRACT: Barotropic tide models are single-layer shallow water models forced by an oscillatory
6 body force at the tidal frequency. They are widely used in a variety of applications at increasingly
7 high spatial resolutions to take advantage of new high-resolution bathymetric datasets. Here we
8 investigate the impact of the small-scale roughness present in such bathymetry on the solutions
9 obtained by these models. It is shown that rough topography induces a form stress that scales
10 with the depth variance relative to the mean depth, $\overline{h'^2}/\bar{h}^2$, and is out-of-phase with the tidal flow.
11 As such, this force extracts no energy from the tide, but can significantly damp or amplify tidal
12 elevations depending on the resonant properties of the basin. Due to these effects, barotropic
13 tidal models only converge with increasing resolution once the variance of the topography is fully
14 represented. These results have important implications for improving the accuracy of barotropic
15 tide models.

16 **1. Introduction**

17 Single-layer (barotropic) shallow water models are routinely used to represent the ocean surface
18 tide, and depending on the application, may be preferred over more realistic multi-layer (baroclinic)
19 models. Example applications include inverse modelling of the surface tide (e.g., Egbert and
20 Erofeeva 2002), investigation of future tides associated with rising mean sea levels (e.g., Pickering
21 et al. 2017; Schindelegger et al. 2018), and deep-time tidal evolution studies (e.g., Green et al. 2017;
22 Daher et al. 2021). The first barotropic tide models (Pekeris and Accad 1969; Hendershott and Munk
23 1970; Accad and Pekeris 1978) were run at relatively low horizontal resolutions of approximately
24 2° , commensurate with the computational power and limited bathymetric data available at that
25 time. However, modern barotropic tide models are now regularly run at resolutions of 0.1° or
26 higher (e.g., Stammer et al. 2014) with model topographies constructed from bathymetric datasets
27 with nominal resolutions of up to 15 arc seconds (or $1/240^\circ$; e.g., GEBCO 2025). As such, these
28 models explicitly resolve not only the ocean basins themselves (as in early models) but also a large
29 portion of the small-scale roughness associated with the ridges, hills and seamounts that are widely
30 distributed over the seafloor. Here we develop a theory to describe the impact of including this
31 small-scale roughness in barotropic tide models.

32 The accuracy of barotropic tide models has generally increased with higher horizontal resolution
33 (e.g., Egbert et al. 2004; Müller 2011; Schindelegger et al. 2018; Huang et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2024;
34 Yang et al. in rev.), although these improvements have now largely stalled. Tidal elevations, energy
35 dissipation and elevation errors in forward models tend to converge with increasing resolution at
36 around $1/12^\circ$ (Egbert et al. 2004; Schindelegger et al. 2018; Yang et al. in rev.), with a non-negligible
37 error always present despite significant model tuning. The improvement with resolution is attributed
38 to some combination of better represented ocean basin geometry, shoreline configuration, and rough
39 bathymetry. The basin geometry is critical because the tides are a resonant phenomena, such that
40 small changes in basin widths and shapes can have a significant impact on tidal amplitudes globally
41 (e.g., Clarke 1991; Green 2010; Green et al. 2017). The shoreline configuration relates to the
42 resolved coastline shape and the representation of important connections with semi-enclosed seas,
43 such as the Hudson Strait (e.g., Arbic et al. 2007; Webb 2014). Such areas can act as resonators
44 which amplify the open ocean tide, with impacts felt globally (Arbic et al. 2009; Wang et al. 2024).
45 More accurate representation of shorelines and basin geometry through better horizontal model

46 resolution therefore leads to more accurate tidal solutions. It is also argued that the inclusion of
47 more accurate rough bathymetry at higher resolution improves barotropic tide model solutions
48 (e.g., Egbert et al. 2004; Huang et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2024), but the evidence in this case is less
49 clear. By ‘rough bathymetry’, here we mean topographic roughness away from coastlines and of
50 scales much smaller than the basin, such that it does not substantially impact either basin shape
51 or coastline configuration. Egbert et al. (2004) added randomised small-scale roughness to the
52 topography used in their barotropic tide model in order to illustrate its significant impact on the
53 solution. However, while the impact is clear, whether the inclusion of higher resolution rough
54 bathymetry *improves* the barotropic solution is less so.

55 It is well known that small-scale roughness significantly impacts the surface tide via *baroclinic* —
56 as opposed to barotropic — effects. Indeed, the primary energy sink for the tide is via near-bottom
57 turbulence driven by strong tidal flows on shallow continental shelves, often represented in models
58 via a linear or quadratic bottom drag (e.g., Dong et al. 2023). In addition, there is a substantial
59 body of work investigating the topographic stress associated with internal tide generation, although
60 most studies have focused on the associated energy flux rather than the stress itself (e.g., Bell
61 1975; Baines 1982; Llewellyn Smith and Young 2002; Khatiwala 2003; Nycander 2005, 2006;
62 Shakespeare et al. 2020, 2021a,b). In radiating wave regimes (where tidal frequency ω exceeds the
63 local inertial frequency f) the oscillatory topographic stress is (at least partly) in-phase with the
64 tidal flow and removes energy from the tide. However, in non-radiating regimes ($\omega < f$), or where
65 wave reflections occur, the stress may have out-of-phase components which remove no energy from
66 the tide, but nonetheless significantly modify its amplitude (Shakespeare et al. 2020, 2021b). In
67 barotropic tide models these baroclinic wave dynamics are not directly resolved and (in forward
68 ‘free-running’ models) are routinely parameterised via a ‘wave drag’, the coefficient of which
69 is typically tuned to achieve a solution that best matches observations (e.g., Egbert et al. 2004;
70 Green and Nycander 2013; Buijsman et al. 2015; Arbic et al. 2018). The wave drag is associated
71 with topographic scales that produce internal tides, which equate to roughly ~ 100 - 200 km (for
72 mode-1 internal tides in the open ocean; e.g., Zhao et al. 2016) and smaller. However, topography
73 at these scales is also being directly resolved in modern high-resolution barotropic tide models,
74 where it will exhibit barotropic dynamics, despite its scale being such that we would expect (and
75 indeed are parameterising) baroclinic wave dynamics. In this sense, modern barotropic tide models

76 suffer from a resolution mismatch with high horizontal resolution capable of resolving internal
77 tide-generating topography, but very low vertical resolution (i.e., 1 layer) incapable of representing
78 the actual generation of waves. Permitting baroclinicity in a model (i.e., through the addition of
79 a second vertical layer) improves the barotropic tide solution (Arbic et al. 2004), but the details
80 of the dynamics at play remain uncertain. Therefore, here we seek to understand nature of the
81 (unphysical) barotropic dynamics induced by sub-mode-1 topography in barotropic tide models
82 and its influence on the tidal solution obtained.

83 The paper is laid out as follows. In §2a we derive an expression for the drag coefficient associated
84 with tidal flow over small-scale rough topography in a barotropic ocean and compare with previous
85 expressions for the baroclinic stresses. In §2b we demonstrate the significant impact of this
86 barotropic stress on the tide in situations of gradually increasing complexity. Lastly, in §3 we
87 summarise and discuss the application of our results for improving the representation of tides in
88 barotropic models.

89 2. Results

90 a. Theory

91 As a simple model for barotropic tides, here we consider the linearised shallow-water equations
92 in one spatial dimension (x) but permitting flow in the orthogonal direction (y):

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} - fV = -gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} + hF_x - \tau_x, \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + fU = -\tau_y, \quad (1b)$$

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} = 0. \quad (1c)$$

93 Here $(U, V) = (uh, vh)$ are the tidal volume fluxes in the (x, y) Cartesian directions, F_x a tidal body
94 force, f is the Coriolis parameter, η the free surface elevation, g the acceleration due to gravity, and
95 h the ocean depth. For completeness, we have also included a generic stress (τ_x, τ_y) , which will
96 be used in the subsequent section. The linearisation assumption made in these equations is valid
97 for $\eta \ll h$. The topographic stresses on the fluid, which are the focus of this work, correspond to
98 the integration of the term $-gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}$ over space; that is, they occur due to correlations of topographic

FIG. 1. Schematic of a tidal channel defined by basin-scale topography \bar{h} on which is superimposed small-scale roughness h' (shown in grey). This roughness induces small-scale variations in free surface height η' , leading to mean stresses $\tau = \frac{g}{h} \overline{h' \frac{\partial \eta'}{\partial x}}$ when integrated over the topography ($x_0 - \frac{l}{2} < x < x_0 + \frac{l}{2}$) which modify the basin-scale free surface height $\bar{\eta}$.

and free surface height variations. For convenience, here we will assume a tidal body force F_x that is constant in space (and periodic in time). While both the assumptions of 1D geometry and spatially-uniform F_x may be avoided, they simplify the analysis below and are sufficient for our purposes of elucidating the key dynamics of the problem.

We now define $U = \Re[\widehat{U} e^{-i\omega t}]$ with $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and similarly for the other variables. We also define $\widehat{\tau}_x = r_x \widehat{U}$ and $\widehat{\tau}_y = r_y \widehat{V}$, where r_x and r_y are the (potentially complex valued) linear drag coefficients in each spatial direction. With these definitions, (1) may be reduced to

$$gh \frac{i\omega - r_y}{i\omega} \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} + ((i\omega - r_y)(r_x - i\omega) - f^2) \widehat{U} = (i\omega - r_y) h \widehat{F}_x, \quad (2)$$

with $\widehat{\eta}$ then derivable from \widehat{U} via

$$\widehat{\eta} = \frac{1}{i\omega} \frac{\partial \widehat{U}}{\partial x}. \quad (3)$$

While it is trivial to solve (2) numerically (see §2b), here we instead wish to seek an expression for the stresses induced by small-scale rough topography and evaluate their impact on the basin-scale flow. To ease the derivation, in this section we will set $r_x = r_y = 0$ such that (2) simplifies to

$$\frac{gh}{\omega^2 - f^2} \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} + \widehat{U} = \frac{i\omega}{\omega^2 - f^2} h \widehat{F}_x. \quad (4)$$

114 As illustrated in Fig. 1, we consider a domain of zonal width L_x , defined by a basin-scale (mean)
 115 topography which we denote \bar{h} . Superimposed on this mean we consider topographic variations
 116 h' of much smaller scale, such that the total ocean depth is $h = \bar{h} + h'$. Formally we can define
 117 the overbar operator as a spatial average over widths l that are large compared to the small-scale
 118 variations in topography,

$$\bar{h}(x_0) = \int_{x_0-l/2}^{x_0+l/2} h(x) dx. \quad (5)$$

119 The small-scale topography will induce variations in fluxes (and free surface elevation) which may
 120 be similarly defined; e.g., $U = \bar{U} + U'$. Substituting these decompositions into (4) yields

$$\frac{g}{\omega^2 - f^2} \left(\bar{h} \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} + h' \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2} + \bar{h} \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2} + h' \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} \right) + \widehat{U} + \widehat{U}' = \frac{i\omega \widehat{F}_x}{\omega^2 - f^2} (\bar{h} + h'), \quad (6)$$

121 which, after applying the spatial average ($\bar{\quad}$) becomes

$$\frac{g}{\omega^2 - f^2} \left(\bar{h} \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} + \underbrace{h' \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2}}_* \right) + \widehat{U} = \frac{i\omega \widehat{F}_x}{\omega^2 - f^2} \bar{h}. \quad (7)$$

122 This equation (7) governs the evolution of the basin-scale flow, which is influenced by the small-
 123 scale topography through the topographic stress (the * term) associated with those scales,

$$\widehat{\tau} = \frac{g}{\bar{h}} \overline{h' \frac{\partial \widehat{\eta}'}{\partial x}} = \frac{g}{i\omega \bar{h}} \overline{h' \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2}}. \quad (8)$$

124 A general formulation for this stress can be determined by finding an expression for the small-scale
 125 flux \widehat{U}' in terms of the large-scale flux \widehat{U} (rather than the forcing \widehat{F}_x). At this point we need to
 126 introduce the assumption that the fine scale topographic variations are small in amplitude relative
 127 to the mean depth, $h' \ll \bar{h}$. We can then combine (6) and (7) to eliminate \widehat{F}_x , and drop any terms
 128 of second or higher order in perturbation quantities. This leaves

$$\left(\frac{\lambda_0}{2\pi} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2} + \widehat{U}' = \widehat{U} \frac{h'}{\bar{h}}, \quad (9)$$

129 where $\lambda_0 = 2\pi\sqrt{g\bar{h}/(\omega^2 - f^2)}$ may be recognised as the wavelength of the barotropic tide, which
 130 has typical scales of ~ 5000 km in the open ocean. As long as the small topographic scales are *much*
 131 smaller than λ_0 , then the second term in (9) is much smaller than the first and may be neglected;
 132 thus

$$\frac{\partial^2 \widehat{U}'}{\partial x^2} \simeq \frac{\omega^2 - f^2}{g\bar{h}^2} h' \widehat{U}. \quad (10)$$

133 This expression (10) may be substituted into the equation for the stress (8) to give $\widehat{\tau} = \sigma \widehat{u} = \sigma \widehat{U}/\bar{h}$,
 134 where

$$\sigma = -i \frac{\omega^2 - f^2}{\omega} \frac{\overline{h'^2}}{\bar{h}^2}, \quad (11)$$

135 is known as the *drag coefficient*. Therefore, in a barotropic flow the stress due to small-scale
 136 topography depends only on its variance relative to the mean depth, $\overline{h'^2}/\bar{h}^2$, but not on the shape
 137 or scale of that variation. A broad mid-ocean ridge and a sequence of abyssal hills will have the
 138 same impact on the basin-scale flow so long as their root-mean-square height $\sqrt{\overline{h'^2}}$ is the same.

139 We further observe that σ in (11) is purely imaginary. This result implies that the topographic
 140 stress τ is 90° out-of-phase with tidal flux \widehat{U} and therefore extracts no energy from the tidal flow
 141 in the time mean. In fact, this result follows directly from (1), which says that U differs by a time
 142 derivative from η (1c) — implying it is 90° out of phase — and therefore the topographic stress
 143 $-gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}$ term in (1a), which is in phase with η , does zero work. That is, averaging $W = -gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} U$
 144 over a tidal period yields identically zero. Similar imaginary drag coefficients have previously been
 145 derived by Shakespeare et al. (2020) in the context of internal tide reflections (in baroclinic radiating
 146 wave regimes) and evanescent internal waves (in baroclinic non-radiating regimes). Regardless of
 147 its phasing, the presence of this topographic stress is critical to setting the tidal amplitude in the
 148 presence of small-scale roughness, as we show in the next section.

149 *b. Solutions in a tidal channel*

150 In this section we demonstrate the importance of the out-of-phase barotropic stress associated
 151 with small-scale topography via explicit solutions in a tidal channel (as drawn in Fig. 1), which can
 152 be thought of as a zonal transect of an ocean basin. The governing equation (2) is solved subject
 153 to boundary conditions of $\widehat{U} = 0$ at the edges of the channel, $x = 0$ and $x = L_x$. This equation can
 154 either be solved using the full topography h with purely real drag coefficients $r_x = r_y = \alpha$ to obtain

155 the full velocity \widehat{U} , or else with $h = \bar{h}$, $r_y = \alpha$, and $r_x = \alpha + \sigma$ to obtain the basin-scale flow \widehat{U} with
 156 small-scales parameterised through the imaginary drag coefficient σ as per (11)

157 Before proceeding with numerical solutions for more complex cases (where h and σ vary in
 158 space), we first consider the simplest case of a uniform depth basin ($\bar{h} = \text{const.}$) with uniform
 159 (parameterised) small-scale roughness ($\overline{h'^2} = \text{const.}$) where an analytic solution is available. In this
 160 case, (2) becomes

$$g\bar{h}\frac{i\omega - \alpha}{i\omega}\frac{\partial^2\widehat{U}}{\partial x^2} + ((i\omega - \alpha)(\alpha + \sigma - i\omega) - f^2)\widehat{U} = (i\omega - \alpha)\bar{h}\widehat{F}_x, \quad (12)$$

161 which may be solved using a Fourier series approach, the details of which are given in the Appendix.
 162 Here we simply quote the result for $\alpha = 0$:

$$\widehat{\eta} = \frac{4\widehat{F}_x\bar{h}}{L_x(\omega^2 - f^2)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \left(\frac{(2n-1)\lambda_0}{2L_x} \right)^2 + \frac{\overline{h'^2}}{\bar{h}^2} \right]^{-1} \cos\left(\frac{(2n-1)\pi}{L_x}x\right). \quad (13)$$

163 The maximum ($x = 0$) tidal amplitude of this solution is illustrated in Fig. 2a, along with solutions
 164 for cases with $\alpha > 0$ (see Appendix). The solution exhibits resonance when the width L_x is close to
 165 an odd multiple of half-wavelengths of the barotropic tide, λ_0 , with the strength of these resonances
 166 modulated by the (real) drag α . The effect of adding small-scale roughness is to shift the resonances
 167 to slightly smaller basin widths L_x . Thus, as shown in Fig. 2b, the addition of roughness increases
 168 the tidal amplitude when the basin width is less than the resonant value ($L_x \lesssim \lambda_0/2$) and reduces the
 169 tidal amplitude when the basin width is greater than the resonant value ($L_x \gtrsim \lambda_0/2$). This pattern
 170 repeats for subsequent resonances at larger multiples of the barotropic half-wavelength. The impact
 171 of the small-scale roughness is significant, especially at near-resonant conditions; however, even
 172 well away from resonance (e.g., $2L_x/\lambda_0 = 1.5$) a roughness of 30% of the mean depth causes a
 173 20% change in the tidal amplitude.

180 We now turn our attention to a more realistic case where both the large- and small-scale to-
 181 pographies are spatially varying, and a numerical solution to (2) is required. The intent of
 182 this example is to demonstrate that the theoretical description of the stresses induced by rough
 183 topography presented above — and the associated resonant dynamics — is accurate, even
 184 in the case of more realistic and complex topography. Fig. 3a displays the three topogra-

174 FIG. 2. Tidal amplitudes in a uniform depth basin of varying widths with small-scale roughness of varying
 175 amplitude. (a) Maximum tidal amplitude as a function of basin width L_x (expressed in multiples of tide half-
 176 wavelengths $\lambda_0/2$) for small-scale roughness $\sqrt{h'^2}/\bar{h} = 0$ and 0.3. The amplitude is non-dimensionalised by
 177 $\frac{4\widehat{F}_x\bar{h}}{L_x(\omega^2-f^2)}$. Solutions are shown for both $\alpha = 0$ (dashed) and $\alpha/\omega = 0.02$ (solid). (b) The ratio of the maximum
 178 tidal amplitude in a solution with small-scale roughness to that without. Ratios are shown for $\sqrt{h'^2}/\bar{h} = 0, 0.1,$
 179 $0.2,$ and 0.3 (see legend) with $\alpha/\omega = 0.02$ and frequency $\omega/f = 1.41$.

185 phies of interest: (i) a smooth basin topography, $h = \bar{h}$, with either (ii) 50 km-wavelength si-
 186 nusoidal variations added, $h' = 0.1\bar{h}\cos(2\pi x/50\text{km})$, or (iii) a mid-ocean ridge/trough added,
 187 $h' = h_0\cos(2\pi(x-L_x/2)/200\text{km})W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a window function (here a double error
 188 function) and $h_0 = 2500$ m. The sinusoidal topography is similar to the previous example in that
 189 it contributes a spatially uniform $\overline{h'^2} = 0.1^2\bar{h}^2/2$, whereas the ridge topography is associated with
 190 a localised topographic variance and stress, $\overline{h'^2} = h_0^2W(x)^2/2$.¹ We compute the tidal amplitudes
 191 for each of the three topographies for basin widths just below (Fig. 3b) and just above (Fig. 3c)
 192 resonance. The behaviour is consistent with that of the analytic solution described above: below
 193 (above) resonance the tidal amplitude is higher (lower) for the rough topographies as compared
 194 to the smooth basin. Fig. 3b,c also shows the solutions computed using $h = \bar{h}$ with the rough
 195 topography parameterised via σ (with $\overline{h'^2}$ as detailed above). It is notable that these solutions are

¹The factor of 1/2 in each expression arises from the average of a sinusoid squared over a period.

198 FIG. 3. Tidal channel solutions with idealised topography. (a) The large-scale basin topography (black), with
 199 a central ridge added (red), and with sinusoidal roughness added (blue). (b) Tidal elevations for each topography
 200 when the basin width is 98% of the half-wavelength of the tide. Note that the smooth basin-only topography
 201 has *lower* tidal amplitude. (c) Tidal elevations for each topography when the basin width is 101% of the half-
 202 wavelength of the tide. Note that the smooth basin-only topography has *higher* tidal amplitude. In both (b) and
 203 (c) the solutions with parameterised drag for each topography are indicated by dashed cyan lines (which overlay
 204 the corresponding full topography solutions). Parameters used here are: M_2 tidal frequency $\omega = 1.41 \times 10^{-4}$
 205 s^{-1} , $f = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, forcing $\widehat{F}_x = 10^{-7} m s^{-2}$, and zero real drag, $\alpha = 0$. These parameters correspond to a tidal
 206 half-wavelength of $\lambda_0/2 = 6261$ km based on the basin-depth of 4000 m.

196 indistinguishable from those using the explicit rough topography, indicating the accuracy of our
 197 description of the small-scale topographic stress, i.e., (11).

207 Lastly, we consider an example using real ocean topography to investigate how the tidal solution
 208 changes with topographic resolution and at what resolution we would expect a tidal model to
 209 converge. We obtain topography for a zonal transect of the Atlantic basin at $40.15^\circ N$ (Fig. 4a)
 210 from GEBCO (2025). The large-scale ‘resolved’ topography is defined through a smoothing

211 operation

$$\bar{h} = \frac{\int_0^{L_x} h(x_0) S(x - x_0, l) dx_0}{\int_0^{L_x} S(x_0, l) dx_0}, \quad (14)$$

212 where S is a Gaussian of width l ,

$$S(x, l) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}l} \exp\left(-\frac{4x^2}{l^2}\right). \quad (15)$$

213 The small-scale variance $\overline{h'^2}$ (and hence σ) is then defined by applying the same smoothing operator
214 to $(h - \bar{h})^2$. Fig. 4 shows the basin topography (a) and small-scale variance (b) for a selection of
215 smoothing widths from $l = 150$ to 5 km, along with solutions for the tidal amplitude (c) and phase
216 (d). The solutions show that (in this example) the presence of small-scale roughness damps the
217 tidal amplitude and shifts the amphidrome (node) towards the west. This latter effect is due to the
218 non-uniform distribution of topographic variance, with more located in the eastern than western
219 side of the basin. The tidal amplitudes change by more than a factor of 10 in parts of the channel
220 — especially near the amphidrome — illustrating once again the significant effect of small-scale
221 roughness. It is clear from the figure that the ~ 5 km smoothed solution is close to converging to
222 full (unsmoothed) topography solution. This convergence at around 5 km is consistent with results
223 from a global barotropic tide model using the same topographic dataset (Yang et al. in rev.).

231 To interrogate this convergence further, Fig. 5a displays the root-mean-square (RMS) tidal
232 amplitude as a function of smoothing width. The 5 km-smoothed solution has an RMS amplitude
233 that differs from the full topography solution by 1 mm (1.5 %), which reduces to 0.2 mm (0.3%)
234 for the 1 km-smoothed solution. This convergence behaviour is consistent with the amount of
235 topographic variance unresolved at each smoothing level (Fig. 5b), with less than 3% of the
236 variance being omitted at 5 km. The unresolved variance can be represented using our theory (11),
237 with the corresponding RMS tidal amplitude shown in Fig. 5a (red). These cases with smoothed
238 topography and parameterised roughness are much closer to the full solution compared with the
239 unparameterised cases, but they remain imperfect, especially at larger smoothing widths where
240 the assumption that $h' \ll \bar{h}$ breaks down (see the red and blue lines in Fig. 4b, near $x = 0$ and
241 L_x). Nonetheless, the theory has sufficient accuracy to explain the behaviour of the solutions for

224 FIG. 4. M_2 tide solutions in an ‘Atlantic channel’ model at various resolutions. (a) Cross-section of the Atlantic
 225 basin at 40.15°N (black) and smoothed at various levels (see legend) using a Gaussian smoothing. Topography
 226 is sourced from GEBCO (2025). Inset plot shows an enlargement of the region enclosed by the rectangle. (b)
 227 The topographic variance relative to ocean depth for each level of smoothing. (c) Tidal amplitude for full and
 228 smoothed topographies. (d) Tidal phase for full and smoothed topographies. Parameters used here are: M_2 tidal
 229 frequency $\omega = 1.41 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $f = 9.38 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (corresponding to 40.15°N), forcing $\widehat{F}_x = 10^{-7} \text{ m s}^{-2}$, and
 230 real drag $\alpha = 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

242 different resolutions of topography; that is, barotropic tidal solutions will converge consistent with
 243 the fraction of topographic variance resolved by the model.

244 FIG. 5. Convergence of ‘Atlantic channel’ model (see previous figure) with increasing resolution of topography.
 245 (a) Root-mean-square (RMS) tidal elevation as a function of Gaussian smoothing lengthscale l for solutions
 246 without (black) and with (red) parameterised barotropic drag for the unresolved scales. The elevation for the
 247 full topography solution is shown by the dotted black line. (b) The fraction of unresolved topographic variance
 248 (drag coefficient) as a function of smoothing lengthscale (black), relative to the 150 km smoothed topography;
 249 i.e., $\langle \sigma_l \rangle / \langle \sigma_{150km} \rangle$, where $\langle \rangle$ denotes spatial averaging. The variance fraction (as a function of half-wavelength)
 250 as calculated via a Fourier transform of h'_{150km} is also shown for comparison (blue solid).

251 3. Discussion

252 Here we have developed a theory to describe the forces generated by small-scale, rough topogra-
 253 phy in barotropic tide models. The forces are always out-of-phase with the tidal flow and therefore
 254 extract no energy from the tide, but nonetheless can significantly modify its amplitude and phase,
 255 especially when close to resonant conditions. The forces were shown to scale with the small-scale
 256 topographic variance relative to the basin depth, $\overline{h'^2} / \bar{h}^2$, implying that a tidal model will only
 257 converge with increasing resolution when this resolution is sufficient to fully capture the variance
 258 of the topography. We demonstrated this result explicitly by solving for the tide in an Atlantic-like
 259 channel at various resolutions and showed behaviour consistent with global model studies (Egbert
 260 et al. 2004; Yang et al. in rev.).

261 However, in addition to explaining the convergence behaviour of barotropic tide models, our
 262 results bring into question whether (and how) these models should represent such small-scale
 263 topography. As discussed in §1, in the real world (and in baroclinic models), topography of
 264 sufficiently small-scale will induce baroclinic rather than barotropic dynamics. We would expect
 265 the barotropic-to-baroclinic transition to occur near the lengthscale of the first baroclinic mode,
 266 which has wavelength $\lambda_1 = 2N\bar{h}/\sqrt{\omega^2 - f^2}$ for buoyancy frequency N , corresponding to typical
 267 values of 100 – 200 km in the deep, mid-latitude ocean (for the M_2 frequency). The implication
 268 is that the inclusion of topographic variance at scales smaller than ~ 100 km in a barotropic tide
 269 model induces barotropic stresses (as described herein; i.e., (11)) that do not exist in the real world.
 270 Instead, the actual stresses will be the baroclinic ones previously described by Shakespeare et al.
 271 (2020). In the radiating wave regime (when $\omega > f$, which covers the vast majority of the ocean for
 272 semidiurnal tides) the baroclinic stress includes an in-phase component associated with the energy
 273 transfer to internal waves (Shakespeare et al. 2020), which corresponds to the wave drag routinely
 274 parameterised in barotropic tide models (e.g., Buijsman et al. 2015; Arbic et al. 2018). However,
 275 if the radiating waves reflect back to seafloor (i.e., low modes) then an additional out-of-phase
 276 baroclinic stress is induced, which scales similarly to the barotropic stresses described herein,
 277 $\sigma \sim -i(\omega^2 - f^2)\overline{h'^2}/(\omega\bar{h}^2)$ (Shakespeare et al. 2020, see Equation 50 therein), although the precise
 278 magnitude of this stress depends critically on the resonant properties of the wave reflections and is
 279 thus infeasible to predict a priori (Shakespeare et al. 2021b). Unlike the in-phase component, this
 280 out-of-phase baroclinic stress is not accounted for in current tide models. However, since these
 281 models are directly resolving an unphysical but similarly scaling barotropic stress, if the magnitude
 282 of these two stresses matched identically, then the model physics would be correct. Unfortunately,
 283 it seems unlikely this would occur, except by coincidence.

284 Therefore, we now suggest a possible solution to the problem of correctly representing out-
 285 of-phase stresses in barotropic tide models. Given the dependence frequency and topography is
 286 known, a straightforward solution would be to add an out-of-phase drag term to the model equations
 287 with an unknown scaling factor out the front. This scaling factor can then be tuned to achieve an
 288 optimal solution, just as is already routinely done with the scaling factor for the in-phase stress (i.e.,
 289 the wave drag). Such tuning should naturally lead to a representation of the physical baroclinic
 290 out-of-phase stresses that accounts for the complex details of wave reflections, and is appropriately

291 offset to account for the unphysical (but directly resolved) barotropic stresses studied in this work.
292 This tuning approach will be tested in a future work.

293 In summary, the present work has quantified the stresses induced by small-scale topography in
294 barotropic tide models. While the theory was limited to 1D channel geometry for convenience, it
295 can be readily extended to 2D basin geometry if desired; the fundamental nature of the barotropic
296 topographic stresses and resonant behaviour will not change. A remaining theoretical question
297 requiring further investigation is precisely how the barotropic stresses described here transition
298 to the baroclinic stresses described in previous studies as lengthscales reduce and/or stratification
299 increases.

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302 *Data availability statement.* No new data was created by this work. The topographic dataset used
 303 herein is publicly available (GEBCO 2025).

304 APPENDIX

305 Here we give further details of the Fourier series solution for a tidal channel of constant mean
 306 depth \bar{h} and uniform small-scale roughness parameterised by a constant σ , the governing equation
 307 for which is (12). The solution proceeds through a sine decomposition for tidal flux \widehat{U} :

$$\widehat{U} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \widehat{U}_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L_x}x\right), \quad (\text{A1})$$

308 to satisfy the boundary conditions of zero flow at $x = 0$ and $x = L_x$. In addition, the right hand side
 309 (forcing \widehat{F}_x) of (12) may be decomposed using

$$1 = \sum_{\text{odd } n} \frac{4}{n\pi} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L_x}x\right). \quad (\text{A2})$$

310 Substituting these expressions (A1, A2) into (12) leads to an equation for the velocity amplitude
 311 of each horizontal mode \widehat{U}_n ,

$$\left[-\frac{g\bar{h}(i\omega - \alpha)}{i\omega} \frac{n^2\pi^2}{L_x^2} + \left(\omega^2 - f^2 + 2\alpha i\omega + \sigma(i\omega - \alpha) - \alpha^2 \right) \right] \widehat{U}_n = (i\omega - \alpha)\bar{h}\widehat{F}_x \frac{4}{n\pi}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

312 for odd n , and $\widehat{U}_n = 0$ zero otherwise. Substituting the expression for σ (11) into (A3) and
 313 rearranging yields

$$\widehat{U}_n = \frac{i\omega 4\widehat{F}_x \bar{h}}{n\pi(\omega^2 - f^2)} \left(1 + i\frac{\alpha}{\omega} \right) \left[1 - \left(\frac{n\lambda_0}{2L_x} \right)^2 + \frac{\bar{h}'^2}{\bar{h}^2} - \frac{\alpha^2}{\omega^2 - f^2} + i\frac{\alpha}{\omega} \left(-\left(\frac{n\lambda_0}{2L_x} \right)^2 + \frac{\bar{h}'^2}{\bar{h}^2} + \frac{2\omega^2}{\omega^2 - f^2} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (\text{A4})$$

314 for odd n , where $\lambda_0 = 2\pi\sqrt{g\bar{h}/(\omega^2 - f^2)}$ is the wavelength of the barotropic tide. To obtain an
 315 expression for free surface elevation $\widehat{\eta}$ we substitute (A1) into (3) to find

$$\widehat{\eta} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n\pi}{i\omega L_x} \widehat{U}_n \cos\left(\frac{n\pi}{L_x}x\right). \quad (\text{A5})$$

316 The solution for the free surface height is thus:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\eta} = & \frac{4\widehat{F}_x\bar{h}}{L_x(\omega^2 - f^2)} \left(1 + i\frac{\alpha}{\omega}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \left(\frac{(2n-1)\lambda_0}{2L_x}\right)^2 + \frac{\overline{h'^2}}{\bar{h}^2} - \frac{\alpha^2}{\omega^2 - f^2} \right. \\ & \left. + i\frac{\alpha}{\omega} \left(-\left(\frac{(2n-1)\lambda_0}{2L_x}\right)^2 + \frac{\overline{h'^2}}{\bar{h}^2} + \frac{2\omega^2}{\omega^2 - f^2} \right) \right]^{-1} \cos\left(\frac{(2n-1)\pi}{L_x}x\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A6})$$

317 This is the equation used to make the plots in Fig. 2. The $\alpha = 0$ limit of (A6) is presented in the
 318 main text as (13).

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